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DOI:

Published First Online:

Pages: 43-47

How to cite:

POTENTIAL FOR THE FORMATION AND FUNCTIONING OF REGIOPOLIS (FOLLOWING THE EXAMPLE OF BIELEFELD, GERMANY)

ABSTRACT

The examined and theoretically developed topic in the material concerns a "New type" spatial vision of a certain settlement on the part of the EU. A part of the philosophy of Regional Development and the commitment to the subsequent actions of socio-economic development of a territory that is presented in a "new way" is presented. Regiopol definitions are given, the space to be explored and analyzed is indicated. Certain criteria are presented in the territorial study of Regiopol, such as landscape space. An attempt is being made by the author to apply the possibilities of the new requirements of the EC in connection with the Green Policy, to Regiopol.

KEY WORDS

Regiopol, regional development, criteria and urbanization.

JEL

R11, Q11, O29, M21

INTRODUCTION

The birth of Regional Policy must be traced far back in time to the states formed before the new era - India and China, the ancient settlements of Babylon, Ur, Assyria, Phenicia, Uruk and Lagash. In these first formations of "Police (πόλις)" the beginning of the administrative-territorial division of the landscape space, according to the needs of the population, the settlement as a territorial unit and the rulers. Strabo (64 BC - 23 BC) is the founder of the first scientific theoretical knowledge of regional politics and development. In his 17-volume work "Geography" he pays attention to the territorial aspects of demographic processes - the settled and unsettled territories and the connections between them. For the first time, it proposed that the territories and regions be considered according to their natural signs and characteristics, as well as the division of the state into regions. It is considered that the modern scientific theory of regional development (academic orientation) began to form after the 17th century,

when the theory of economic geography was also developed. Regional development as an academic science began to develop in the 19th and 20th centuries. The question of the main stages in the evolution of views on the nature, scope and content of the concept of agglomeration is also important. The first stage, according to the world literature, covers the period from the mid-nineteenth to the beginning of the twentieth century, the second - from the beginning of the twentieth century to the 1970s, and the third - after the 1970s. As far as the Bulgarian scientific literature is concerned, the term 'agglomeration' appeared in the early 20th century and is used in the statistical description of settlements, i.e. as a statistical. Real agglomerations in Bulgaria started to be established from the 1970s onwards. of the last century, when in the highly developed countries began the third stage of their development. It was then that the first publications by our scientists on this subject appeared. One of the strongest and indisputable scientific schools, or the impetus of this science, is the German one, presented by Johann von Thünen (1783-1850), the originator of the theory of the so-called spatial reflection. Develops the first classical model for the localization of agricultural production. Wilhelm Launhardt (Wilhelm Launhardt 1832-1918), created a model for location selection that minimizes transportation costs for raw materials. August Loesch (1906-1945), Walter Kristaler (1893-1969), worked in parallel on the theory of central places, considering their 3 main contributions: they tried to formulate a theoretical dependence for the territorial organization of settlements; investigate the peculiarities of the territorial location of activities from the non-production sphere, justify the hierarchy of settlements (Konakchiev, 2003).

RESULTS AND ANALYSES

On the basis of regional development, which was created by the German classics (school), the construction of modern regionalism began in Germany. It is also basic for the rest of the countries in Europe (Russia, Poland and most of the countries in Eastern Europe).

To distinguish the potential territories in relation to their socio-economic development in 2006, Prof. Jürgen Aring and Prof. Iris Router from the University of Kassel developed a concept of Regiopol. This terminology is associated with regional planning and development of settlement systems, as the concept is formed by the hybrid form of region and Polis (city) – Regiopol, (Aring and Reuther, 2008). In Germany, the concept is applied to smaller cities located outside the metropolitan area, as an independent center developing social, economic, political, administrative, scientific and environmental activities (Regiopol Rostock, 2008).

According to (Regiopol – Deutschiand, 2008), a definition of Regiopol is as follows: "these are always large centers that play a special regional role beyond the aspect of supply and compensation, but due to their smaller size they do not reach the status of a metropolis and in this in a way they can be characterized as "little sisters" of metropolises". Metropolis or metropolis is a thematic term used to define a large city in an urbanized area and is the administrative, economic, social and political center of the region or area in which it is located. The term is applied to territories where the population in them is from 1 to 5 million people or much more. The metropolitan area can unite several cities with different area and number of populations. Transport infrastructure connections are basic for the metropolis, influencing the even distribution of the population throughout the territory. Again, according to (Regiopol – Deutschiand, 2008), another definition of Regiopol is given: "these are the smaller metropolitan cities outside the metropolitan regions and should be understood as the center of regional development. The local location of the society and the attraction of mainly rural areas to the creation of the new structure. These are usually large centers that play a special regional role outside of supply and compensation, but because of their smaller size they fall short of metropolitan status." Geography begins to show interest in agglomeration issues since the 1980s. At that time, the following agglomerations could already be said to exist in our country. - Pernik, Plovdiv, Varna - Devnya, Burgas - Kameno and Veliko Tarnovo - Gorna Oryahovitsa - Lyaskovets. In the 1990s, the agglomeration formed around Pleven. Conurbation refers to an area that covers one or more cities and smaller towns and rural settlements around them. A conurbation links all these settlements of different orders into an area with well-established links of all kinds. About unlike

agglomeration, conurbation usually involves several large towns, the distance between which may be greater but the links are very stable. Famous conurbations in Europe are the Dutch, the UK conurbations around Manchester and Birmingham, and the Ruhr in the Germania. A key factor in the development of urbanisation is the nature of social production. It influences the development of many areas of human activity and the quality of the living environment. It also changes the economic and social structure of the population, the type of culture, etc. Another factor contributing to the development of urbanisation is the increase in transport, administrative, cultural, educational, etc. functions of cities. Their multifunctionality makes it possible to attract a large number of settlers. Linked to this is the improvement of age structure of large and medium-sized cities in many parts of the world. Metropolises (Mieg, 2019), as already discussed, are established and, to a greater extent, completed urban areas and are central places performing the function of administrative units. They develop economically without requiring external intervention due to their nature. For these large urban areas, the problems are related mostly from an environmental point of view. The question of smaller settlements, rural areas and cities for their socio - economic development has always excited regionalists, people from scientific circles, economists, politicians and administration. In terms of population and area, they are smaller than the metropolitan areas distant from the urbanized centers, but regardless of this, they are part of the region and perform socio-economic functions. Small settlements always remain in the "shadow" of big cities, which slows down their development. As a result, the idea of Regiopol was born, as a new concept offering ideas and visions for the socio-economic prosperity of smaller cities. Regiopol is separated from the metropolis as an administrative territory, but the connection between them is preserved through transport infrastructure and migratory mobility of the population. This is a new form of spatial development, on the one hand the formed urbanized area, on the other a new administrative-territorial formation is being created.

According to Prof. Jürgen Aring and Prof. Iris Router, the criteria by which a city can be considered a potential Regiopol are the following:

- ✓ Location outside the metropolitan area
- ✓ Population of the main city or the city network of more than 100,000 inhabitants
- ✓ Infrastructure systems at a high level
- ✓ Great economic importance
- ✓ Location of "Global Players" and "Hidden Champions"
- ✓ Concentration of innovation potential
- ✓ Location of University or several, scientific institutes and units

Of course, there is a procedure for identifying potential Regiopol in Germany, but we will not go into it here and specify the scientific concepts and characteristics. They are not subject to visualization in order not to bore the dear reader. For information, I will point out that the identification of Regiopol is based on:

- ✓ Population of the main city or the city network of more than 100,000 inhabitants
- ✓ Location outside the metropolitan area
- ✓ Potential for knowledge and innovation - location of a university

Out of a total of 82 main German cities that were examined according to the aforementioned search criteria, 19 are located in the main cities of metropolitan regions and another 30 are in a metropolitan area. For the remaining 33 large cities, the gravity thesis is consulted, cities are classified according to mass and distance parameters. And the main basis for calculation is the population of the respective city.

The first German region set to transform into a Regiopol is Rostock. It is the largest city in the province of Mecklenburg-Vorpommern in Germany with a population of 202,735 inhabitants as of 31.12.2011. Its area is 181,26 km², with an average population density of 1118 h/km². In order to popularize the idea in other parts of the country, various groups from business, administration, scientific circles and public figures are working in this direction. The characteristics (the same or similar can be applied to another settlement) of the city with which it can be transformed are defined:

Location; Port city; Economic and Social Center; Large city by population; University Center; Transport location of the city – European transport axis; Tourist destination or urban tourism; Research activities and others.

The region, Regiopol Bielefeld is the territory that develops this kind of regional concept. City in Germany with an area of 257,92 km², in the province of North Rhine-Westphalia with a population as of 31.12.2010 of 323,270 inhabitants, at an average density of 1,253 h/km². The economic structure includes small and medium - sized businesses, there are a number of family businesses in the area. A diverse center for the arts and entertainment. Old university center. It is this mixture that makes Regiopol the Bielefeld region, a colorful and lively area with a high degree of attractiveness and significant potential for development in economic terms. Rural communities contribute to a higher quality of life with a wide variety for the development and implementation of tourism activities. These socio - economic activities reflect on the number of the population in a positive direction, which in turn leads to an increase in natural growth. The inter-municipal association to the Regiopol region was agreed in 2016, spatially aligned with Regiopol Bielefeld and includes ten more partner municipalities of Bielefeld (Gütersloh, Herford, Bad Salzuflen, Halle, Steinhagen, Enger, Oerlinghausen, Leopoldshöhe, Spenge and Werther, as of December 2017 the partnership in this colorful region aims to strengthen competition between municipalities in the long term, as well as improve the quality of life.

CONCLUSION

From a modern point of view, the projects related to the development of the settlement system, and in particular those for Regiopol, should be aimed directly at the population in the smaller municipalities, which are connected to the larger administrative center. This new type of settlement must be given its chance for development and funding, just like large urban centers. A condition is created to preserve the population in rural municipalities without losing the center-periphery connection. The reduction of migration processes and the pressure on urbanized spaces is a key element to the development of this "new type" of space. The formation of administrative structures of this type, secured by built or under construction infrastructure, creates conditions for the normal functioning of society in all its aspects of development. On the other hand, Regiopol, as a forming territorial unit according to the European NUTS classification, including in its nomenclature also smaller settlements, outside the urbanized area, creates a perspective for creating suburban (Petrov and Marinov, 2020) spaces. In connection with the new European policy related to the implementation of the "European Green Pact" (EC 2019 - 2024), Regiopol can become a "platform" for implementing the introduced requirements for Sustainable Development of the Old Continent - new infrastructure (social - economic) corresponding to the Green Policy philosophy, such as promoting climate action. The third industrial revolution, the ecological transition, represents a huge opportunity for European industry, as it leads to the creation of markets for clean technologies and products again according to (EC 2019 - 2024). In developing countries, urbanisation is one important factor in accelerating their socio-economic development. Modern demands on the quality of life, the needs of high education and qualification, high technology and developed culture are causing the number of people in these countries to grow continuously, who are leaving the villages and looking for a way to live in cities. In their case, the rapid increase urban population growth can prove dangerous. Most often, the urbanisation process is difficult to control because these countries do not have the sufficient economic, financial and legal capacity to do so. Most characteristic of developing countries is precisely the high growth rate of urban population. Urbanisation is extensive. Large rural masses are moving towards cities not only because of the above factors, but very often driven by poverty and unemployment in villages. Many of them cannot adapt to urban conditions. In developing countries, there is usually one big city, which is usually the capital, and the rest cities are much smaller in population their size and functions performed. The strong development of a city (in smaller countries) or several (in larger ones) gives rise to a host of problems, the most acute being that of the high concentration of functions in one, rarely in several places and the impossibility of

development of secondary centers. For the territories of the other European countries, members of the EU, the implementation, formation and development of Regiopol is possible. Taking into account the specifics and characteristics of the socio-economic profile for each country.

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